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CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

SATURDAY- 13 DECEMBER 2025

- **Literature**
- **Language and Discourse**
- **Communication, Journalism, Education Sciences, Psychology and Sociology**
- **History, Political Sciences, International Relations**
- **Social Sciences**

The conference is organised in partnership by:

"Alpha" Institute for Multicultural Studies

"Gh. Șincai" Institute for Social Sciences and the Humanities

"Dimitrie Cantemir" University of Tîrgu Mureș

A WORD FROM THE PRESIDENT OF THE CONFERENCE

Dear Guests,

Having established a certain tradition in the recent years, the International Conference *LITERATURE, DISCOURSE AND MULTICULTURAL DIALOGUE* (now at its 13th edition) intends to unite emerging scholars, as well as prestigious researchers from different fields of radical relevance for the contemporary society, a society that is supposed to secure its future not only on the economic and ecological level, but also on the spiritual one. Literature, the cultural discourses as well as the arts gain new connections and dimensions through fundamental changes and structural progress, so that the social end-results of education and research becomes extremely important. It is a fact that in our postmodern times, we live in a society of knowledge, from which we benefit directly in our everyday life, but to the risks and dangers of which we are at the same time exposed. *Non scholae sed vitae discimus* (*We do not learn for the school, but for life*) becomes a creed that every academic institution has to put into practice by means of its activities. It is essential that the path between education and research is very short, especially in academic systems. Research generates new knowledge, creates a favourable atmosphere for change, and provides people with information and data which help them to become aware of the mysteries of the universe and to make the most

of their activity in all fields of knowledge. In this interesting and captivating century, to the noble mission of educating the younger generations we must also add the fruit of the efforts in research, materialized in interesting works and papers, together with ideas generated by the creative ability which ennobles the personality of the academic.

I wish to express my hope that this scientific event will take place under the most favourable auspices and that it will represent a remarkable starting point for further evolution and development in the field of knowledge. Let this international conference provide a good opportunity for us to gain and transfer knowledge, to generate new theories in the world of science – essential aspirations of any contemporary research.

Prof. IULIAN BOLDEA, PhD
President of the *LDMD 13* Conference

SATURDAY – 13 DECEMBER 2025

LITERATURE

Moderators: Prof. Iulian Boldea, PhD, UMFST Tîrgu Mureş; Assoc. Prof. PhD Lavinia Magdalena Bănică, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest; Assoc. Prof. PhD Mirela Radu, „Titu Maiorescu” University of Bucharest

1. Iulian Boldea, Prof., PhD, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Tîrgu Mureş, *LUCIAN BLAGA – BETWEEN FICTION AND AUTOBIOGRAPHY*
2. Lavinia Magdalena Bănică, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Piteşti, *ON ESCAPING THE WORLD THROUGH ALLEGORY. ROMANIAN MEDIEVAL LITERARY METHODS-NOTES*
3. Mirela Radu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Titu Maiorescu” University of Bucharest, *A DOCTOR'S LITERATURE-FORM OF DISSIDENTSHIP*
4. Alba Simina Stanciu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, „Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *METAPHYSICAL DIMENSIONS OF FORM AND "EMPTY SPACE" IN CONTEMPORARY SCENOGRAPHY*
5. Oana-Andreea Ghiţă-Pîrnuţă, Senior Lecturer, PhD, “Transilvania” University of Braşov, *DELVING INTO LOVE JOURNEYS AND MULTIPLE NATIVE AMERICAN NARRATIVE THREADS*

6. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *ILLNESS AS AN ABSURD ACT, THE PLAGUE AND THE GAME OF SLAUGHTER*
7. Iulian Băicuș, Lecturer, PhD, University of Bucharest, *MIRCEA ELIADE - PORTUGUESE DIARY*
8. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *AN ENTERTAINING LADY BY OSAMU DAZAI: AN ANALYSIS*
9. Irina-Ana Drobot, Lecturer, PhD, Technical University of Civil Engineering, Bucharest, *REACTIONS TO SUCCESS IN THE SHORT STORY CHIYOJO BY OSAMU DAZAI*
10. Lizeta-Cristina Furtună, Lecturer, PhD, "Valahia" University of Târgoviște, *THE MYTH OF RETURN AND THE DILEMMA OF SELF-SALVATION. REPRESENTATIONS IN ION AGÂRBICEANU'S WORK*
11. Iudit Călinescu, Lecturer, PhD, Romanian Language Institute, Bucharest, University of Szeged, Hungary, *KEY ASPECTS AND ISSUES RELATED TO MYTH CLASSIFICATIONS*
12. Mihaela-Anca Ogășanu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Oradea, *TAONGA-THE DILEMMA OF BELONGING: TRACING KAHU'S TRAJECTORIES IN REVEALING AND FACING HER BICULTURAL IDENTITY*
13. Cristina Miron, Lecturer, PhD, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *CHRONOTOPES AND INTIMATE SPACES: BAKHTIN, BACHELARD, AND MULTICULTURAL IDENTITY IN ELIF SHAFAK'S THREE DAUGHTERS OF EVE*
14. Cristina Veronica Andreescu, Lecturer, PhD, University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Carol Davila" Bucharest, Roxana Corina Sfetea, Prof.,

PhD, University of Medicine and Pharmacy “Carol Davila” Bucharest, *PARATHETIC WRITING IN THE 16TH CENTURY IN WALLACHIA*

15. Corina Guță, Independent Researcher, Dana Camelia Diaconu, Lecturer, PhD, “Valahia” University of Târgoviste, *POETRY IN ROMANIAN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE: A HISTORICAL AND STYLISTIC ANALYSIS*
16. Antonia Pop, Assist. Prof., PhD, Partium Christian University, *NEGOTIATED IDENTITIES IN PETER SHAFFER'S WHITE LIARS AND BLACK COMEDY*
17. Mihaela Popuța, Assist. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, *TRANSNATIONAL VOICES AND THE LANGUAGE OF DIPLOMACY IN CONTEMPORARY FICTION: CHIMAMANDA NGOZI ADICHIE'S AMERICANAH AND PAUL AUSTER'S 4 3 2 1*
18. Felicia Mich, PhD, Anghel Saligny Technological High School, Turț, Satu Mare, *BETWEEN SHIFTING BORDERS AND INTERSECTING IDENTITIES: SORIN TITEL'S TETRALOGY*
19. Mirabela Lungu, Independent Researcher, Dana Camelia Diaconu, Lecturer, PhD., “Valahia” University of Târgoviște, *RHYMES AND SMILES: INTEGRATING ENGLISH POETRY IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION*
20. Cosmina Roșu, PhD, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *DECADENCE, CORRESPONDENCE, AND INSTRUMENTALISM*
21. Dorina Nela-Trifu, PhD, Costin D. Nenițescu Technical College, Pitești, Ion Barbu Theoretical High School, Pitești, *DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN THE NOVEL CONCERT DIN MUZICĂ DE BACH*

22. Emanuel-Daniel Sărmășan, Assist. Prof., PhD Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, *VALERIU ANANIA. MEDICAL HISTORY. BRIDGES AND STEPS TOWARD RESURRECTION*
23. Ramona Buruiană, PhD, “Virgil Madgearu” Economic College, Galați, *RURAL REFLECTIONS IN THE INTERWAR WOMEN'S NOVEL: GEORGETA MIRCEA CANCICOV, POENI. THE MOLDAVIANS*
24. Camelia Bof (Hreban), PhD Student, “Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *THE INITIATORY DIMENSION OF PETRE ISPIRESCU'S FAIRY TALES*
25. Adriana Chioaru, PhD Student, „Ferdinand I” National College, Bacău, *A CONCEPTUAL EMBLEM: "INVOLUNTARY EXPRESSIVENESS"*
26. Ionela-Leontina Floroiu (Dănuț), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *ASPECTS OF ORALITY IN THE WORK OF ION HELIADE RĂDULESCU*
27. Adriana Chioaru, PhD Student, „Ferdinand I” National College, Bacău, *EUGEN NEGRICI AND THE METAMORPHOSES OF THE PARADIGM IN THE APPROACH TO ANCIENT LITERATURE*
28. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *HUMAN FRAGILITY AND DIVINE HOPE IN PSALM 142: A LITERARY AND LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF THE HEBREW TEXT AND THE SEPTUAGINT*
29. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *SAMUEL BECKETT AND THE EXPLORATION OF THE RADIO MEDIUM: WRITING WITH SOUND AND SILENCE*

30. Paul-Cristian Albu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *FIDELITY AND CREATIVITY IN THE TRANSLATION OF TRAVEL LITERATURE*
31. Dimitrie Andrei Borcan, PhD Student, „Ovidius” Univeristy of Constanța, *ROOTLESSNESS IN ARTHUR MILLER’S “A VIEW FROM THE BRIDGE”*
32. Dimitrie Andrei Borcan, PhD Student, „Ovidius” Univeristy of Constanța, *MORAL DRAMA IN ARTHUR MILLER’S „ALL MY SONS”*
33. Alexandra Ruscanu, PhD Student, „Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *THE CONFIGURATION OF FEMALE IDENTITY IN THE “SBURĂTORUL” LITERARY CIRCLE*
34. Centa-Mariana Solomon, PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *HORIA LOVINESCU’S LITERARY CHOICES, AS REVEALED IN THE CONTEMPORARY PRESS*
35. Centa-Mariana Solomon, PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *HORIA LOVINESCU’S LITERARY CHOICES, AS REVEALED IN THE PRESS OF THE TIME*
36. Mariana Cocieru, PhD, Moldova State University, Coordinating Scientific Researcher, Institute of Romanian Philology „Bogdan Petriceicu-Hasdeu”, *PROTECTIVE RITES AND MECHANISMS FOR NEUTRALIZING THE POWER OF ARCHETYPAL DEATH DEMONS IN ROMANIAN TRADITION*
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38. Oana Bădăluță, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *VERISIMILAR AND DREAMLIKE CINEMATIC SPACES OF SCREANINGS; CRONOTOPIC GUIDE MARKS IN THE NOVEL LORD OF THE RINGS*

39. Adela Sava (Codreș), PhD, University of Craiova, *HISTORY AND POLITICS IN THE WORK OF IRÈNE NÉMIROVSKY*
40. Adriana Maria Călugăr (Cutean), PhD Student, “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *CONFIGURATIONS OF THE CONCENTRATORY SPACE – CONTEXTUAL DELIMITATIONS*
41. Alina Ghițu (Cazac), PhD Student, „Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *THE ALTERNATIVE WORLDS OF THE AILING BODY IN LILIANA COROBCA’S NOVEL, THE LADYBUG*
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43. Andreea-Maria Popescu, PhD Student, *THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE TRAUMA IN CRITICAL AND FICTIONAL INTERPRETATIONS OF EXILE LITERATURE*
44. Maria Bîscal (Oprea), PhD Student, “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *CHILDHOOD BETWEEN TRAUMA AND HOPE IN DIASPORIC PROSE: THE CASE OF MIGUEL GANE*
45. Dana Burlacu, PhD Student, Moldova State University, *LOTIS DOLËNGA OR POETRY AS A METAPHOR FOR TRAVEL*
46. Diana Grumeza, PhD Student, Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *ALTERITY AND IDENTITY IN ROMANIAN INTIMATE JOURNAL*
47. Laura Gheorghită, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *POSTMODERNISM IN THE NOVELS OF MIRCEA CĂRTĂRESCU*
48. Ingrid Nistor-Sopon, PhD Student, Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *PUTTING WAR ON TRIAL IN*

THE TRIAL OF LUCULLUS: BRECHT'S UNDERMINING OF HERO WORSHIP

49. Mădălina Bărbulescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *CEZAR IVĂNESCU: A MYSTICO-RELIGIOUS PERSPECTIVE ON POETRY*
50. Maria-Nicoleta Pop, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE VOICE OF ALTERITY: THE DIALOGUE OF IDENTITY IN MIHAIL SEBASTIAN'S NOVEL TWO THOUSAND YEARS*
51. Laura Dorina Nistor (Danc), PhD Student, "1 Decembrie 1918" University of Alba Iulia, *THE PLAYFUL AND THE DRAMATIC IN ARGHEZI'S POETRY FOR CHILDREN*
52. Nora-Eugenia Ciocănea, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *SPACE AND DIALOGUE BETWEEN CULTURES IN ALEXANDRE DUMAS' NOVEL THE COUNT OF MONTE CRISTO*
53. Paula Danaricu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *THE LIFE OF A BOOK: THE EVOLUTION OF "THE PORTRAIT OF A LADY" BY HENRY JAMES*
54. Ioana-Cristina Pătrună, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology "Politehnica", Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *RURAL TYPOLOGIES IN POST-WAR PROSE: DINU SĂRARU'S REALISM, FĂNUȘ NEAGU'S FANTASTIC AND ȘTEFAN BĂNULESCU'S MYTHICAL*
55. Rebeca-Daniela Stănescu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology

- “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *SPACE AND BEING IN URMUZ'S WRITINGS*
56. Valentina Gherghina, PhD Student, “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *THE ALGORITHMIC REWRITING OF MULTICULTURAL DIALOGUE IN SNOW CRASH*
57. Manuela Varga, PhD Student, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, *THE ALTERNATIVE WORLDS OF FANTASY LITERATURE—A MEANS OF ESCAPE FROM EVERYDAY LIFE*
58. Alexandra-Ana Chiprian, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *EXILE IN SERGEI DOVLATOV'S VISION - A CASE STUDY OF THE NOVEL A FOREIGN WOMAN*
59. Maria Lazăr, PhD Student, “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *CONNOTATIONS OF FIRE IN CONNECTION WITH BLINDNESS IN THE LIGHT THAT GOES OUT, BY MIRCEA ELIADE, AND AUTO DA FÉ, BY ELIAS CANETTI*
60. Iuliana-Elena Asoltanei, PhD Student, “Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *PERFORMANCE AS LIFE: SHAKESPEAREAN INTERTEXT AND THE CONSTRUCTION OF IDENTITY IN M.L. RIO'S IF WE WERE VILLAINS*
61. Maria-Linuca Biligan, PhD Student, “Babeș-Bolyai” University of Cluj-Napoca, *“THE FAULKNERIAN REVOLUTION” AND RURAL COLLECTIVE PSYCHOLOGY IN SORIN TITEL'S PROSE*
62. Daniela Turcu (Bobu) F., PhD Student, “Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *ADRIAN ZOGRAFI AND HIS IDENTITY PROJECTIONS IN PANAIT ISTRATI'S PROSE*
63. Andra-Diana Morar, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica

Bucharest, *NARRATIVES OF THE URBAN UNDERGROUND: THE CULTURAL, PHENOMENOLOGICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL CONSTRUCTION OF THE METRO IN CONTEMPORARY ROMANIAN LITERATURE AND PUBLIC IMAGINATION*

64. Alina Neculachi, PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *ANTE- AND INTERWAR INTERTEXTS IN THE NEOMODERNIST NOVEL*
65. Teodora Fărăgău, MA, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureș, Ionela Cecilia Șulea, Assist. Prof., PhD, „Dimitrie Cantemir” University of Târgu Mureș, *TIME AND TEMPORALITY IN LUCIAN BLAGA'S POETRY*
66. Mihaela Miroiu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *FANTASTIC ELEMENTS IN FOLK TALES FROM VÂLCEA*

LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE

Moderators: Prof. Sorin Guia, PhD, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași; Prof. Floriana Popescu, PhD, “Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați; Assoc. Prof. Simina Badea, PhD, University of Craiova

1. Sorin Guia, Prof., PhD, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *SCIENTIFIC CONCERNS REGARDING SOUTH DANUBIAN DIALECTS*
2. Floriana Popescu, Prof., PhD, “Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *A LINGUISTIC GLIMPSE AT POLYLEXICAL EPONYMISMS*
3. Anca Greculescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, *ENGINEERING STUDENTS’ PERCEPTIONS OF AI-BASED TOOLS FOR LEARNING TECHNICAL VOCABULARY*
4. Anca Greculescu, Assoc. Prof., PhD, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, *DEVELOPING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE MANUAL FOR TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION: A NEEDS ANALYSIS AT UNIVERSITY POLITEHNICA OF BUCHAREST*
5. Simina Badea, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Craiova, *(RE)DISCOVERING METAPHOR IN SPECIALISED LANGUAGES*
6. Iulia Para, Assoc. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, Mihaela-Elisabeta Proteasa-Popuța, Assist. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, *FUNCTION AND FORM OF ENGLISH SLANG IN THE DIGITAL COMMUNICATION OF ROMANIAN YOUTH*
7. Iulia Para, Assoc. Prof., PhD, West University of Timișoara, Monica Elena Cranta, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *WHEN LANGUAGE GETS IN THE WAY: LINGUISTIC BARRIERS AND LINGUISTIC INTEGRATION IN EUROPEAN HIGHER EDUCATION*

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9. Maria-Elena Milcu, Assoc Prof. habil PhD, “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, Elena Raluca Gheorghe, PhD Student, “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *TERMINOLOGY AND SPECIALIZED LANGUAGES OF GASTRONOMY: STUDY OF CONCEPTUAL AND LINGUISTIC EVOLUTION*
10. Roxana Grunwald, Lecturer, Phd, “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, Anca Mureșanu, Lecturer, Phd, “Lucian Blaga” University of Sibiu, *STYLISTIC DIMENSIONS OF SUBJECT USAGE IN ROMANIAN: FROM GRAMMATICAL ROLES TO EXPRESSIVE STRATEGIES*
11. Ionuț Ștefan, Lecturer, Phd, “Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *THE CHALLENGE OF MULTICULTURALISM FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF EDUCATIONAL POLICIES*
12. Ruxandra Coman, Lecturer, PhD, “Dimitrie Cantemir” Christian University, Bucharest, *ANTI STEREOTYPING THROUGH THE STRATEGIES OF HUMOR AND IRONY IN THE ROMANIAN ADVERTISING DISCOURSE*
13. Iustina Nica, 2nd Degree Scientific Researcher, Phd, “C.S. Nicolăescu-Plopșor” Scientific Research Institute, Romanian Academy, Craiova, *THE ETHNONYM „MISIRLIU” IN THE ROMANIAN CULTURAL SPACE: ORIGIN, EVOLUTION, ONOMASTIC PRESENCE*
14. Cristina Negru, Scientific Researcher, PhD, Institute of Romanian Philology „Bogdan Petriceicu-Hasdeu”, Moldova State University, *STYLISTIC REGISTERS IN ROMANIAN. SPECIFICS OF ADMINISTRATIVE STYLE*
15. Olesea Vîntu, Assist. Prof., Phd, Moldova State University, *THE LINGUISTIC AND DISCOURSE-PRAGMATIC DIMENSION OF NOTARIAL ACTS IN THE PRACTICE OF TRANSLATION FROM ITALIAN TO ROMANIAN*
16. Mădălina Toader, Assist. Prof., Phd, University of Bucharest, *FIXED EXPRESSIONS IN FRENCH ADVERTISING: LINGUISTIC CREATIVITY AND DIDACTIC IMPLICATIONS FOR FLE*

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17. Violeta Marinela Preduț (Dumitru), PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *PARTICULARITIES OF THE DISCOURSE OF MEN’S FASHION*
18. Ica-Emilia Udriște, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *GALA GALACTION – THE TRANSLATOR OF THE BIBLE*
19. Ioana Georgiana Bahrin, PhD Student, “Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, *ASPECTS OF METAMESSAGE IN ROMANIAN ROYAL SPEECHES*
20. Galina Pleșca, PhD Student, Moldova State University, *TEXT TYPOLOGY AT THE CROSSROADS OF LANGUAGE AND DISCOURSE IN MULTICULTURAL CONTEXTS*
21. Ana-Maria Gherghina, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION IN PUPILS DIAGNOSED WITH ADHD*
22. Cristina Kallai, PhD Student, “1 Decembrie 1918” University of Alba Iulia, *GENDER, POPULISM, AND METAPHOR: REFRAMING POLITICAL IDENTITY IN ROMANIA’S EXTENDED 2024–2025 PRESIDENTIAL CAMPAIGN*
23. Maria-Magdalena Diaconu (Marian), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *COMMERCIAL NAMES OF LUXURY GOODS*
24. Elena-Daniela Strigoiu (Marinescu), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *THE ETYMOLOGY OF THE CONCEPT OF AUGMENTATION*
25. Georgiana-Adelina Floroiu, PhD Student, National University of Science and Technology “Politehnica”, Bucharest, University Center of Pitești, *MEDICAL DISCOURSE AND DOCTOR–PATIENT VERBAL INTERACTION: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS*
26. Adela Maria Măgurean, PhD Student, West University of Timișoara, *LEGAL TRANSLATION AS A TYPE OF SPECIALIZED TRANSLATION*

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27. Maria Cristina Bogdan, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *GREEK-LATIN ETYMONS IN THE LEXICON OF MINERALOGY*
28. Réka Incze (Kutasi), Phd Student, UMFST „G. E. Palade” of Târgu Mureş, *ANALYSING INTERNAL CONFLICT IN ANOREXIA DISCOURSE ON TWITTER/X*
29. Gabriela-Cristina Podani (Spiridon), PhD Student, University of Bucharest, *GASTRONOMIC TERMINOLOGY IN COMMUNIST ROMANIA AND IN THE GERMAN DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC*
30. Denis-Alin-Florin Diaconu, PhD Student, University of Craiova, *ABOUT A REFERENCE PHILOLOGICAL EDITION: BUDAI-DELEANU, ION, WORKS, 1-2, CRITICAL EDITION BY FLOREA FUGARIU, INTRODUCTORY STUDY BY AL. PIRU, BUCHAREST, MINERVA, 1974-1975*
31. Mirela-Simona Gurău (Rusu), PhD Student, „Dunărea de Jos” University of Galați, *TRANSLATIONAL INFLUENCES ON ROMANIAN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY*
32. Eugenia-Ioana Ciobanu (Vlad), PhD Student, University of Craiova, *ASRO STANDARDIZATION PRINCIPLES AND METHODOLOGY. OVERVIEW*
33. Maria-Loredana Simionovici (Grosariu), “Ștefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, *THE TRIPLE-DEFINED THEORETICAL MODEL: PRODUCTIVE RECEPTION, AUTOBIOGRAPHY, AND SOLIPSISM IN MODERN LITERARY HERMENEUTICS*
34. Elena-Georgiana Udrescu, Phd Student, University of Craiova, *THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SPECIALIZED LEXICON – COMMON LEXICON – INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENTIFIC LEXICON (FINANCIAL DOMAIN)*

**COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM, EDUCATION
SCIENCES, PSYCHOLOGY AND SOCIOLOGY**

Moderators: Prof. Teodor Pătrăuță, PhD, „Vasile Goldiș” West University of Arad; Assoc. Prof. Maria Pleșca, PhD, „Ion Creangă” State Pedagogical University, Chișinău, Republic of Moldova; Assoc. Prof. Laura Ioana Leon, „Grigore T. Popa” University of Medicine and Pharmacy, Iași

1. Teodor Pătrăuță, Prof., PhD, “Vasile Goldiș” West University of Arad, *THE INTERCULTURAL PARADIGM IN EDUCATION*
2. Claudiu Coman, Prof., PhD, “Transilvania” University of Brașov, Monica Elena Cranta, PhD Student, University of Craiova, Raluca-Maria Șerbănescu, BA, Transilvania University of Brasov, *LANGUAGE BARRIERS IN STUDENT MOBILITY: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF INTEGRATION CHALLENGES AMONG ERASMUS PARTICIPANTS*
3. Claudia Florina Pop, Assoc. Prof., PhD, University of Oradea, *NAVIGATING THE DIGITAL ERA: PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR UNIVERSITY TEACHERS’ DIGITAL COMPETENCE*
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Section/ Secțiunea: HISTORY

Title/ Titlul:

Octavian Goga in Alfred Rosenberg’s Perception: Political Friendship, Ideology, and Antisemitism (1935–1938) / Octavian Goga în percepția lui Alfred Rosenberg: prietenie politică, ideologie și antisemitism (1935–1938)

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Alfred Rosenberg; Octavian Goga; antisemitism; Nazi ideology; Romanian–German relations; interwar Romania; Veturia Goga; National Socialism; political diaries; Central and Eastern Europe, 1935–1938.

Abstract/ Rezumat:

Octavian Goga in Alfred Rosenberg’s Perception: Political Friendship, Ideology, and Antisemitism (1935–1938). This study examines how Alfred Rosenberg – one of the principal ideologues of the National Socialist Party and a long-standing intellectual associate of Adolf Hitler – perceived and promoted the politician Octavian Goga during the years 1935–1938. Our study is based on Rosenberg’s German-language diaries and their Romanian edition. The diary reveal a sustained political and personal relationship, reinforced through repeated meetings of Rosenberg with both Octavian Goga and Veturia Goga. Rosenberg interpreted this connection as a useful ideological alliance grounded in shared antisemitic and far-right convictions and in a similar vision for reshaping the political order in Central and Eastern Europe.

In Rosenberg’s view, Goga was the Romanian political figure most compatible with the strategic aims of National Socialist Germany, and he portrayed him as capable of steering Romania toward a consistently antisemitic and pro-German course. Unlike the Legionary Movement, which Rosenberg does not mention at all and with which he records no interaction, Goga appeared to him as a predictable, cultivated, and doctrinally aligned leader. Rosenberg self-identified as an “old Nazi” and an intellectual architect of the nazi regime, frequently criticizing Goebbels and the German Foreign Office for their alleged lack of ideological depth.

Although the fall of the Goga government in February 1938 surprised him, Rosenberg expressly welcomed the initiation of systematic antisemitic policies in Romania and hoped

that subsequent governments would continue this political line. By reconstructing this neglected episode in Romanian–German relations, the study provides a new perspective on how key Nazi elites understood Romania’s internal dynamics during these years.

REZUMAT:

Octavian Goga în percepția lui Alfred Rosenberg: prietenie politică, ideologie și antisemitism (1935–1938) / EN: Octavian Goga in Alfred Rosenberg’s Perception: Political Friendship, Ideology, and Antisemitism (1935–1938).

Lucrarea noastră analizează modul în care Alfred Rosenberg – unul dintre principalii ideologi ai Partidului Național-Socialist și un apropiat intelectual al lui Adolf Hitler – l-a perceput și promovat pe Octavian Goga în anii 1935–1938, pe baza jurnalelor sale publicate în limba germană și în ediția românească. Însemnările lui Rosenberg relevă existența unei relații politice și personale constante, consolidate prin întâlniri repetate cu Octavian Goga și cu Veturia Goga, relație pe care ideologul nazist o interpreta ca pe o alianță durabilă, întemeiată pe un set comun de principii, în special antisemitismul doctrinar.

Rosenberg îl considera pe Goga politicianul român cel mai compatibil cu proiectele naziste și îl prezenta în jurnal ca fiind capabil să orienteze România către o linie antisemită și pro-germană. Spre deosebire de Mișcarea Legionară, pe care nu o menționează și cu care nu admite nicio legătură, Rosenberg vedea în Goga un lider predictibil, cultivat și ideologic convergent cu direcția național-socialistă. Rosenberg se auto-prezenta ca „vechi nazist”, un „intelectual al revoluției naționale-socialiste”, criticându-i pe Goebbels și pe diplomații Ministerului German de Externe pentru lipsa lor de „profundzime doctrinară”.

Prăbușirea guvernului Goga în februarie 1938 l-a surprins, dar Rosenberg se declara mulțumit că guvernul Goga declanșase primele politici antisemite sistematice în România, politici pe care Germania nazista le voia continuate. Studiul evidențiază astfel un episod puțin analizat în istoriografia româno-germană și oferă o perspectivă nouă asupra felului în care elitele naziste înțelegeau dinamica politică românească din acei ani.

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